

1 **Loss of neuropeptide FF receptor 1 expression in human epilepsy.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Differential expression refers to relative increases or decreases in expression when comparing two
7 groups, conditions, settings, treatments, or populations. Relative increases or decreases in this case are
8 equivalent to higher or lower expression of the gene without a necessary increase or decrease between
9 the conditions.

10 In an attempt to discover and define the most significant changes associated with cancer in humans,
11 scientists studying cancer have historically focused on identifying the presence of mutations in genes
12 rather than identifying expression changes associated with that gene. While mutations can be complex,
13 associated with variegated functional changes that cannot necessarily be ascribed to gain or loss of
14 function associated with increased or decreased expression, the majority or a major portion of the change
15 associated with the mutation will almost always be associated with gain or loss of function - that is to say,
16 the mutation will need to be defined as being equivalent to increased or decreased expression. We
17 pioneered the use of quantitative and computational methods using whole transcriptome technology to
18 identify therapeutic targets based on differential and increased expression in human cancer; that is, the
19 gene product is among the greater changes in the transcriptome when comparing the two conditions, the
20 gene product (transcript) is present in higher quantities, and is thus amenable to “neutralization” of its
21 activity, which presumably supports cancer survival, by pharmacologic inhibition.

22 Similarly, scientists studying neurologic diseases or psychiatric diseases like Parkinson’s Disease and
23 schizophrenia have focused on using genome-wide association studies to identify disease-associated
24 causal variants, overlooking identification of over-expressed genes that are therapeutic vulnerabilities
25 without regard to that expression change being the result of a germline inherited variant or de novo
26 acquired mutation.

27 We used here whole transcriptome technologies to measure total transcription in the brain and identify the
28 most significant gene expression changes in the brains of humans with epilepsy, a serious medical
condition that results in seizures, or abnormal electrical activity in the brain. We report here the discovery
of loss of neuropeptide FF receptor 1 (*NPFFR1*) expression in humans with epilepsy.